

Assessing LoRaWAN radio propagation for smart parking service: An experimental study

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ABSTRACT

The increase of the population living in cities has put a lot of pressure in urban transportation systems. It comes, among other things, with noteworthy air pollution, time and energy wastage, and drivers' discomfort due to parking spots scarcity. Finding a parking spot has become a major problem for drivers. To overcome this problem, smart parking services that detect parking spot occupancy status and inform drivers about their availability have been proposed. The deployment of these solutions is reducing the costs associated to traffic jams or gas consumption. However, one of the main challenges faced when planning and deploying this kind of service is the communication technology used by the parking sensors, which are typically buried under the asphalt, as it has to cover large areas of the city in the most cost-effective way. In this paper, we analyze the behavior and performance of a LoRaWAN network supporting the smart parking service in the city of Santander. The sensors and network deployment are described and the thorough experimental evaluation of the network behavior is presented. The goal of this assessment is to provide insights that could be helpful for better understanding the key factors affecting the communication. The long-termed analysis of the parking sensors deployments studied, have allowed us to derive an experimental propagation model that could be useful for the planning of city-scale IoT infrastructures employing LoRaWAN networks as their wireless access technology. Moreover, we have also analyzed the behavior of the LoRa wireless network in order to evaluate the possibility of leveraging network information to increase the confidence on smart parking sensor readings through AI-based predictors.

1. Introduction

The demographic explosion that started in the 1950's has caused an exponential growth of urban areas, causing pollution, overexploitation and poverty, among others. Besides, this is a growing concern, as the urban population is increasing over time and, according to the United Nations (UN), up to the 68% of the total world population will live in cities by 2050 [1]. As a result, city livability and citizens' quality of life are being deteriorated over time. In this scenario, the Smart City concept has been proposed as a solution to improve the city livability employing novel technologies as tools to overcome new challenges that have emerged from overpopulation. Among these technologies, Internet of Things (IoT) becomes of utmost importance as a mean to monitor the city and ease the decision-making process. Moreover, the IoT market keeps growing at a remarkable pace, and forecasts predict up to 27 billion of connections by 2025 [2], partly due to the impact of Smart City projects [3] and, in particular, smart parking ones [4].

Smart parking has become one of the key services within the Smart City, as a mean to reduce the road occupancy and the pollution.

Therefore, IoT-based parking services are already a reality, leveraging low-power communication technologies as their deployment environment, usually in the asphalt, lacks of power supply and their access for battery replacement is a non-trivial problem [5]. In this context, Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN) technologies are well-suited for this type of services, and used not only in Smart Cities, but also in rural areas [6,7] or other mobility-related applications [8], which can even provide satellite navigation-independent positioning thanks to their features [9]. The communication technologies covered under LPWANs include licensed technologies, such as Narrow Band IoT (NB-IoT) or LTE-M, as well as unlicensed ones, from which we can highlight Sigfox and LoRaWAN [10].

Among the existing LPWAN technologies, LoRaWAN has several advantages that makes it suitable for smart parking services based on sensor devices deployed outdoors [11]. The use of LoRaWAN is actually growing thanks to its low-power consumption and long-range communication, sacrificing the throughput, which is not critical for parking monitoring.

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Although some smart parking solutions based on LoRaWAN can already be found in the literature [12,13], either they do not delve deep into the network performance evaluation [14–16], or they do not present their results based on a real long-term urban deployment [17]. In [18], we conducted a preliminary study on the design and evaluation of a LoRaWAN-based smart parking deployment, putting special emphasis on the characteristics of these types of deployments and extracting some conclusions about the challenges and key aspects that should be considered for the deployment of this kind of networks.

The key contributions of this paper focus on three main aspects. Firstly, we have analyzed the performance evaluation of a smart parking service based on a very large experimental dataset that comprises ten months of data extracted from the a smart parking deployment. Secondly, we have carried out a comprehensive analysis over the available network information, mainly the Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), in order to derive an experimental propagation model that could be used for the planning and deployment of similar LoRaWAN networks in urban scenarios. Finally, we have evaluated how network related information, such as the RSSI, can be used to increase the confidence in the information received from the parking sensors. For this, we have trained and assessed the accuracy of several AI-based classification models so that the predictions made using these models could be used to support the level of confidence in the observations made by the parking sensors.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents an overview of both, the LoRa and LoRaWAN communication technologies. Section 3 describes in detail the LoRaWAN-based smart parking service and the deployment carried out in Santander, as well as the system that enables the LoRaWAN data collection. Then, in Section 4 we present the performance evaluation of the smart parking service and discuss the results emerged from the use of LoRaWAN. Section 5 describes the analysis carried out in order to derive a wireless propagation model for LoRa-based communications in urban environments that has been created as a result from statistically assessing the received signal strength traces gathered during the ten months in which the smart parking service has been running. Furthermore, Section 6 presents the evaluation of different AI classification algorithms designed to increase the confidence in the sensor readings by using received signal strength information to predict parking spot status. Finally, Section 7 summarizes the lessons learned and the future work.

2. LoRa and LoRaWAN overview

Even though the terms “LoRa” and “LoRaWAN” are frequently used interchangeably, they actually refer to different communication technology concepts. On the one hand, LoRa is a proprietary radio modulation technique that was developed by Semtech and relates to the physical layer. LoRaWAN, on the other hand, is a specification for Medium Access Control (MAC) layer operations. It is an LPWAN protocol built upon LoRa and has been recognized by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU). In this section, we provide an introduction to both communication technologies and emphasize their main features.

2.1. LoRa modulation

LoRa technology uses a modulation based on Chirp Spread Spectrum (CSS) to enable long-range communication. This spread spectrum technique encodes information using wideband linear frequency modulated pulses across three different bandwidths (125, 250 and 500 kHz), and allows demodulation even below the noise level. In addition, LoRa is able to tolerate minor frequency deviations caused by the Doppler effect, and is resilient to fading and multipath environments [19]. This robustness is derived from the support of different Spreading Factors (SF), one of the main features of LoRa.

Table 1
LoRa modulation features (125 kHz bandwidth).

Spreading factor	Bits (Chips per symbol)	SNR limit (dB)	10-byte payload airtime (ms)	Bitrate (bps)
7	128	−7.5	61.7	5470
8	256	−10.0	113.2	3125
9	512	−12.5	205.8	1760
10	1024	−15.0	370.7	980
11	2048	−17.5	823.3	440
12	4096	−20.0	1482.8	250

SFs are a fundamental component of LoRa communication technology, as they are directly linked to the chirps used for data transmission. Chirps are signals characterized by a linear frequency excursion across the channel bandwidth over time, with the frequency decreasing from highest to lowest (down-chirps) or vice versa (up-chirps). SFs, which range from 7 to 12, are determined by the time taken by each chirp. Higher SFs result in greater resilience to noise, as lower Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) is required in the receiver for successful demodulation. In contrast, as CSS defines the number of bits per symbol as 2^{SF} , airtime for a defined payload grows with SF. As a result, greater resilience to noise comes at the cost of increased power consumption and lower data rates. A summary of these characteristics can be seen in Table 1, where the airtime is calculated considering the LoRaWAN protocol specification. LoRa SFs are inherently orthogonal, hence they behave as noise to each other. LoRa also incorporates an error correction scheme, typically with a 4/5 coding rate, and is designed for use in the sub-GHz spectrum. In Europe, LoRa operates at the 868 MHz frequency band, with a bandwidth of 0.3 MHz per channel, and is regulated by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI).

2.2. LoRaWAN specification

The LoRa Alliance maintains and proposes the LoRaWAN specification, currently at version 1.1 [20], with the aim of optimizing the data transmission rate and energy consumption for meeting the demands of IoT devices. It features end-to-end protected bidirectional communication through a star-of-stars network topology in which gateways (GWs) relay messages between end-devices and a network server. The three fundamental components of the LoRaWAN architecture are defined below:

- End-devices (ED) are sensors or actuators wirelessly connected to a LoRaWAN network. They are able to send (uplink) or receive (downlink) traffic to/from a network server through LoRaWAN GWs.
- Gateways (GW) play a crucial role in the LoRaWAN network. They serve as relay between EDs and the network server. They demodulate the uplink messages received from EDs and modulate downlink messages the other way around. While EDs are typically power-constrained devices, GWs are not and are usually connected to the Internet through traditional high-speed network technologies (e.g. Wi-Fi or Ethernet). EDs communicate with the GWs in an N-to-N pattern, with their uplinks broadcasted and receivable by any GW.
- The Network Server (NS) is the core component in the LoRaWAN architecture backend. It is responsible of receiving all uplink messages from EDs and exposing them to the application layer. GWs and Network Server follows a N-to-1 communication pattern. Besides, downlink messages are transmitted to each particular ED through the GW that has the best SNR for the received uplinks.

LoRaWAN protocol offers an Adaptive Data Rate (ADR) feature that allows devices to select the optimal SF based on the SNR received by the GW. This feature aims to use the lowest possible SF, reducing power consumption while maximizing packet delivery ratio.

Fig. 1. Byda parking sensors.

Besides, to avoid collisions and maximize energy efficiency as much as possible, LoRaWAN limits the usage of the wireless channel. In particular, regulatory authorities impose restrictions on the channel usage, limiting transmissions to a 1% duty cycle per node.

In summary, thanks to the characteristics of LoRa and LoRaWAN, battery-powered devices are meant to achieve [21]:

- Low power consumption: depending on various factors, such as signal strength and usage patterns, devices can remain operational for more than 10 years without requiring a battery replacement.
- Long-range communication: devices can communicate up to several kilometers (around 5 km in urban scenarios and up to 15 km in open areas under Line of Sight (LOS) propagation conditions).

3. Smart parking service

The LoRaWAN smart parking service presented in this paper has been deployed in the city of Santander. The service relies on parking sensors that are buried under the asphalt to monitor the occupancy status of individual parking spots. There is one parking sensor per parking spot. Deployed parking sensors are manufactured by Byda [22] and shown in Fig. 1.

In terms of sensing, parking sensors utilize radar technology to detect the presence of vehicles parked above them. By filtering out extraneous objects (e.g. tree leaves), the sensors are able to accurately report on the occupancy status of individual parking spots.

In terms of communications, parking sensors implement the ADR mechanism to optimize the energy consumption and reduce the airtime as much as possible. Sensors report their status following a twofold approach: (i) upon an asynchronous event, triggered by a status change; and (ii) periodically, sending a beacon every hour that includes the occupancy status. Lastly, the application-level protocol specifies that all the transmissions are confirmed. Thus, parking sensors wait for an explicit acknowledgment and force a retry if they do not receive it. After a certain number of failed retransmissions, parking sensors assume that they have lost connectivity and trigger a reboot that originates a new join procedure.

The chosen deployment areas aim to create two heterogeneous scenarios in terms of usage and communication coverage, and leverage the pre-existing LoRaWAN network infrastructure in Santander, which comprises 10 GWs distributed throughout the city, as shown in Fig. 2.

3.1. Downtown deployment

The first deployment scenario is at “Paseo Menéndez Pelayo” street, located in the city downtown. This area is characterized for having a high building density and a moderate to high traffic density caused by drivers searching for an available parking spot. The scenario comprises a two-way street with parking spots located at both sides of the road. A detailed image of this deployment was included in [18].

The deployment in this scenario consists of 45 parking sensors, with the closest LoRaWAN GWs located at a distance of 250 to 385 m. Furthermore, the number of buildings and the lack of LOS between the GWs and parking sensors make this scenario challenging in terms of coverage.

Fig. 2. Gateway distribution and deployment areas.

3.2. Lighthouse deployment

The second deployment scenario takes place on an outdoor parking lot near Santander’s lighthouse, located in the “Avenida del Faro” avenue. This area has a completely different profile than the previous scenario, being a more natural setting on the outskirts of the city. While it usually has low traffic density, it is a tourist and leisure area which becomes crowded during specific periods depending on weather conditions and vacation periods. Additionally, this location is situated at one of the highest points in the city, providing LOS to different LoRaWAN GWs with distances of up to 3 km.

A total of 24 parking sensors have been deployed in this area. A detailed image of this deployment was included in [18]. It is important to note that the deployment benefits from the presence of a LoRaWAN GW installed in the same area. This means that the parking sensors are in close proximity to the GW, with distances ranging from only 25 to 60 m. This results in an almost ideal scenario in terms of communication.

3.3. Smart parking system

The smart parking system has two central components beyond the IoT infrastructure deployed in the city of Santander: (i) the LoRaWAN Network Server and Application Server, for which we have leveraged the collaborative solution provided by The Things Network (TTN); and (ii), an ad-hoc developed component named Parking Data Extractor.

TTN provides a secured MQTT broker offering a subscription-based mechanism to receive LoRaWAN uplinks received by any GW. These messages also include network-related metadata (e.g. Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), Frame counter).

The Parking Data Extractor component is responsible for obtaining and processing all the uplinks generated by the smart parking infrastructure. It retrieves all the packets received by the MQTT subscription and store them in a local database. Finally, it sends the parking service information to the SmartSantander platform [23], making it available for the city and other value-added services. The whole system is depicted in Fig. 3.

4. Performance evaluation

The performance evaluation of the deployed LoRaWAN-based parking sensors in both scenarios has been conducted by analyzing a dataset containing 599 128 packets demodulated by the various GWs. Of these, 368 998 packets were received from devices deployed in the downtown

Fig. 3. Smart parking service back-end system.

Fig. 4. Number of packets received per LoRaWAN GW and the corresponding SF.

scenario, accounting for 61.59% of the total dataset. The dataset covers the period from June 1st 2022 to March 31st 2023.

Fig. 4 shows the distribution of the packets received by GW and the corresponding SF. As expected, the packets distribution clearly depends on the proximity of the GWs to the deployment areas. GWs [kerlink-03] and [kerlink-04] are the closest ones to the Downtown deployment area, while [kerlink-09] is the one located in the Lighthouse deployment area. It is noteworthy that the GW [kerlink-06], located 3 km away from the Lighthouse deployment, receives a considerable number of packets. This indicates that the presence and density of obstacles on the signal propagation path and the received SNR have a greater impact on LoRaWAN deployments than the actual distance. This finding is consistent even for the lowest SF.

To evaluate the behavior of the network, it is crucial to consider the unique characteristics of smart parking services, as the parking status affects signal propagation. Therefore, we have analyzed the impact on the RSSI for both free and occupied parking spots in the different deployments. Fig. 5 shows the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) for each one of them, taking the maximum RSSI value from all the GWs receiving the same packet. As expected, the impact on the RSSI is significantly higher when the parking spot is occupied, with a difference of 5 and 3 dBm between the highest RSSIs for 80% of the received packets in the Lighthouse and Downtown deployments, respectively. On the other hand, the measured RSSI in the Lighthouse deployment is much higher than in the Downtown deployment, as the GW is closer, and the obstacles are almost negligible compared to the Downtown, thus reducing the multipath losses. This can be appreciated in detail in Fig. 6, where the Probability Density Functions (PDF) for both scenarios and states are depicted. In the Downtown deployment, most packets are received with an RSSI of -120 dBm, being the average

RSSI for the occupied status -120.78 dBm. For the free status, the average rises to -117.55 dBm. Conversely, in the Lighthouse deployment, packets are more uniformly distributed across all RSSI values, with an average RSSI of -91.71 dBm and -85.62 dBm for occupied and free parking status, respectively. As already stated, the average attenuation impact of parked vehicles is higher in the Lighthouse deployment. The reason behind this is related to the better coverage conditions of this deployment, where the lack of other obstacles in the LOS does not mask the impact of parked vehicles, as it is the case in the Downtown deployment.

Finally, we have also conducted a study on the influence of distance on the reporting of sensor readings, particularly the changes in RSSI over distance. In order to achieve a broader granularity in terms of distance, we have considered the distance between the corresponding parking sensor and every GW able to demodulate the message. However, as can be seen in either Fig. 7 or Fig. 8, this has the implication that the transmission channel characteristics for the different distance ranges are intrinsically different.

Fig. 7 represents the RSSI at different distances (i.e: different combinations of GW/sensor) for each deployment scenario and different parking status. The marginal axes show independent FDPs, so the area under each density curve sums to 1. Despite the heterogeneity of propagation conditions affecting the RSSI values, a noticeable difference can be observed between both deployments. In the Lighthouse scenario there is a LOS connection to a GW deployed 3 km away, and a non-negligible percentage of messages are received at such distances. However, in the Downtown scenario, messages are almost exclusively concentrated in distances below 500 m, even when there is an alternative GW in the range of 600 m.

As an alternative, Fig. 8 displays the same two dimensions but takes into account the specific spreading factor used in the transmission of the packets. In this particular case, the marginal axes show normalized FDPs, which means that the total area under all densities sums up to 1. Therefore, as the marginal axes can be interpreted as an histogram, we can clearly see the ADR mechanism behavior on both scenarios. In the case of the Lighthouse scenario, the majority of the packets are sent using SF7, while other SFs are almost not used with the exception of SF12, which was occasionally forced during the study time frame for further analysis purposes. On the other hand, in the Downtown scenario, we can clearly see the prevalence of SF12, accounting for the majority of the received packets. Still, some alternative SFs are also selected by ADR, although they are marginal. These results suggest that ADR is effectively adapting the SF to the transmission conditions, with lower SFs being used when the link quality is good, and higher SFs being used when the link quality deteriorates. Based on the concentration of received packets around -120 dBm and the prevalence of SF12, it appears that the Downtown deployment is already at the border of LoRaWAN coverage, particularly for the parking sensors that are farthest away. Despite the LoRa receiver's higher sensitivity, received packets are only slightly below -125 dBm, likely due to noise at the GWs.

Fig. 5. LoRaWAN RSSI CDF for both deployment scenarios.

Fig. 6. LoRaWAN RSSI PDF for both deployment scenarios.

Fig. 7. RSSI versus distance per parking status for both deployment scenarios.

Fig. 8. RSSI versus distance per SF for both deployment scenarios.

5. Experimental propagation model for LoRa-based smart parking deployments in urban environments

The results derived from the analysis carried out in Section 4 show that the observed behavior of high-density urban scenarios, such as the Downtown deployment case, widely differs from the more theoretical behavior expected in suburban or rural scenarios with LOS propagation and EDs over the surface [24,25]. In fact, the results suggest the deployment of LoRaWAN GWs following a picocell approach with coverage ranges below 500 m. However, distance is not the only factor that affects coverage, and additional propagation considerations must be taken into account. In this Section we explore the possibility of deriving a practical LoRaWAN radio propagation model based on experimental analysis that can be applied within these downtown urban environments.

For the development of the model we consider a scenario where a new LoRaWAN-based service plans to take advantage of a pre-existing network infrastructure, as opposed to an integrated solution where GWs are specifically deployed as part of the service. Hence, the prevalence of LoS cannot be guaranteed, leading to higher SFs. In this context, we only consider statistically relevant observations, i.e., those with high probability density in our study. Therefore, based on the analysis of Fig. 8(b), we limit the propagation model to observations received in SF12, as the SF used by the vast majority of them, independently from the distance to the GW. While it is true that using SF12 reduces the available bandwidth and increases packet airtime, which could lead to a higher collision rate, it is also clear that it is the one selected by the ADR mechanism to ensure a proper quality of service in the Downtown deployment scenario. Furthermore, prioritizing quality-of-service over other factors like battery life of end-devices, employing SF12 ensures larger coverage in LoRaWAN-based networks. Hence, prioritizing the service performance in uncontrolled and dynamic conditions, such as the smart parking case.

As a starting point, we propose the following expression as an alternative to the Friis formula for radio propagation in open space [26], or other classical propagation losses models [27,28]:

$$P_R = P_T \cdot G_K \cdot \frac{1}{d^\alpha} \quad (1)$$

$$P_{R(dBm)} = P_{T(dBm)} + G_{K(dB)} - 10 \cdot \alpha \cdot \log(d) \quad (2)$$

where P_T represents the sensor transmitted power, that remains constant throughout the study (14 dBm). G_k denotes a factor that includes transmission gains and losses that can be modeled as constants. Within

this factor we include both the transmitter and receiver antenna gains (2.15 dB and 3 dB, respectively) as well as the shielding losses imposed by the presence of a vehicle on top of the sensor, which have been modeled in Section 4 (~3 dB). Finally, we consider that propagation losses over distance can be modeled as proportional to the inverse of the distance (d , in meters) raised to a power of α . We have not taken the frequency into account because the variation between the different LoRa channels in the 868 MHz band (i.e, the one used in Europe) is not significant and we assume that it remains constant.

Consequently, we reduce the definition of the proposed propagation model to the experimental fitting of ' α ' value. To simplify this process, we take the linear regression as the basis for performing calculations. Nevertheless, as we have discussed, propagation conditions differ for each distance range due to the particular circumstances of each deployed GW. Thus, we suggest calculating the linear regression for each range independently to avoid possible distortions that may appear due to variations in observation density.

In our specific case, each distance range corresponds to a different deployed GW offering coverage to the downtown deployment. Fig. 9 shows the RSSI scatter plot along with the linear regression in the most significant distance ranges of the study, i.e., for GWs [kerlink-03] and [kerlink-04], and for both parking sensor states. Moreover, Fig. 9 shows the linear regression model Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) areas for the different distances. The linear regression model fits the measured RSSI packets, with an overall RMSE for GW [kerlink-03] of 2.06 and 2.84 dB for the Occupied and Free states, respectively; and a RMSE for GW [kerlink-04] of 2.84 and 3.86 dB for the Occupied and Free states as well. We can observe how the shielding effect produced by the presence of vehicles, i.e., the difference between both regressions, is practically constant. Nonetheless, there is a noticeable divergence between signal levels in both distance ranges.

Obviously, the fact that RSSI increases with distance is counterintuitive. This can be attributed to the terrain orography and the unique characteristics of the location of [kerlink-03] with respect to the area where the EDs are deployed. In this particular case, the GW is positioned at a lower height than the deployment itself which, combined with the Z axis predominance of the sensor antenna radiation pattern, makes signal propagation challenging. Moreover, the direct line of sight between the two antennas lies below the terrain level, which likely has a negative effect on the transmission channel due to the Fresnel zones. Last but not least, this GW is placed very close to obstacles, which results in greater losses due to multi-path propagation and further channel impairments. In contrast, GW [kerlink-04] is located in the

Fig. 9. Received RSSI linear regression at SF12 for downtown deployment scenario.

Fig. 10. α value derivation.

high part of the city, on top of a building, which provides better conditions for free space propagation. Therefore, losses due to multipath propagation are much more limited than those due to propagation, as reflections and/or refractions between EDs and the GW are more limited. Furthermore, the fact that the linear regression within the same distance range shows a positive slope also seems counterintuitive. Thus, variations in the EDs position with respect to the GW must be carefully considered. As obstacles are not uniformly distributed, propagation conditions can experiment significant variations. Fig. 9(a) shows that devices located at intermediate distances have a higher concentration of high RSSI values. This is due to the presence of a park area between this zone and the GW, rather than a building acting as an obstacle. As a result, linear regression deviates from its expected logical behavior.

After computing the linear regression for every distance range, we calculate the α values as per Formula (2). Given the distribution of the data sample and the nature of the parking service, it is more representative to extract the value of alpha from the observations with the occupied parking sensor. Still, results obtained using free parking observations are analogous. Fig. 10 shows the calculated raw alpha values obtained from the predicted values by the different linear regressions from all the GWs. By visually inspecting the result, we can clearly identify a negative exponential pattern. However, values over 500 m are far from being representative in our study, as they represent a very low density within the dataset. Nevertheless, as the proposed propagation model is meant to be applied within the boundaries of a downtown urban area LoRaWAN picocell, we consider all the available data for fitting the exponential α curve.

Fig. 10 illustrates two exponential curves referred as *Curve 0* and *Curve 1*. *Curve 0* is computed using all available values of α in our dataset. Nonetheless, a previously mentioned, the specific propagation conditions associated with the location of [kerlink-03] introduce some distortion on the results. Therefore, *curve 1* is computed by ignoring α values in the corresponding distance range for GW [kerlink-03]. We contend that *curve 1* provides a superior fit to be utilized in our proposed propagation model and can be applied to analyze the impact of multipath losses in [kerlink-03]. As a result of our analysis, the α parameter can be expressed as

$$\alpha = 2.63309902 \cdot e^{-1.89563589 \times 10^{-3} \cdot d} + 3.95122607 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 11 represents the actual behavior of the proposed LoRaWAN propagation model in downtown urban areas. This model, which has been derived from experimental results, can be used by practitioners for a preliminary planning in picocell scenarios such as the ones described in the article. Still, radio propagation conditions in dense urban scenarios are heavily dependent of the particular characteristics of such environments, so practitioners are advised to carefully consider the relative positions of the existing GWs with respect to the device deployment areas. The proposed model is almost flat for distances between 300 and 400 m and show a slight growth on the RSSI with the distance over 400 m. While this has been the case in our study, it should be noted that reception conditions and SNR in such distances were far worse, so only a low percentage of messages were received and the quality of service could not be assured. This seems to suggest that at these distances the coverage of LoRaWAN in urban scenarios, such as the one from our case, is at its limits.

Fig. 11. LoRaWAN picocell propagation model in urban areas.

Table 2
Classification algorithms employed.

Classification algorithm	Algorithm parameters
K-Nearest Neighbors	Number of neighbors: 5493 Distance metric: City block Distance weight: Squared inverse Prediction speed: 1300 obs/s
Decision Tree	Maximum number of splits: 1594 Split criterion: Maximum deviance reduction Prediction speed: 1 300 000 obs/s
Neural Network	Number of fully connected layers: 1 First layer size: 100 Activation: ReLU Iteration limit: 1000 Regularization strength (Lambda): 0 Prediction speed: 270 000 obs/s
Support Vector Machine	Kernel function: Gaussian Kernel scale: 0.35 Box constraint level: 1 Multiclass method: One-vs-One Prediction speed: 1700 obs/s

6. AI-based classification for sensor readings' confidence improvement

Among the conclusions that we extracted from the smart parking service performance evaluation that has been presented in Section 4, we have highlighted the correlation that, in the case of the smart parking service, could be observed between the sensor reading (i.e. the observation of free or occupied of a parking spot) and the RSSI. This conclusion led us to investigate the possibility of employing network-related information in order to increase the confidence in a received sensor reading. This way, the smart parking service would not only depend on the capacity of the radar embedded on each of the deployed sensors but could back the radar-based detection with information derived from the LoRaWAN network. In our case, the network-related information that we will be using is the RSSI of the received frames.

The objective is to train AI-based classification models and evaluate whether the predictions that are performed based on these models coincide with the incoming reading. This way, the level of confidence in the incoming reading would be increased. In particular, we have analyzed four different classifiers (namely, Decision Trees, Support Vector Machine, Neural Network and K-Nearest Neighbors) and assessed if the predictions made by each of them could be used to increase the confidence in the sensor readings as we have described above. The idea is to evaluate how different AI-based classification mechanisms

Table 3
Comparative of the performance for the chosen classification algorithms.

Classification algorithm	TPR	TNR	F_1 score	Accuracy
K-Nearest Neighbors	0.734	0.673	0.712	0.703
Decision Tree	0.744	0.663	0.715	0.703
Neural Network	0.751	0.562	0.686	0.657
Support Vector Machine	0.751	0.555	0.684	0.653

can predict the status of a parking spot using two predictors, the RSSI with which the observation is received at the GW, and the euclidean distance between that GW and the originating node.

The first step of the analysis was to gather all the observations that were generated during the execution of the pilot. Specifically, we have employed the data associated to the observations originated from the Downtown deployment, which arrived at two different GWs ([kerlink-03] and [kerlink-04]). As it can be seen in Fig. 4, around 300,000 observations were collected. The resulting dataset contained the parking spot status (i.e. status: free, represented by a boolean False in the dataset; or occupied, represented by a boolean True in the dataset), which is the prediction target; and the observed RSSI and the Euclidean distance, which are the predictors.

Once all the observations are merged into a dataset, we selected four different classifiers and looked for optimized hyperparameters of the classification algorithm. Table 2 summarizes the classifiers that has been used in the evaluation and the parameters used for each of them.

Due to the characteristics of the smart parking service, a large majority of the observations were reporting occupied parking spots. Thus, in order to not bias the resulting classification model, we extracted one training and one test datasets from the overall one that contained the same number of observations reporting a free parking spot than indicating that it is occupied. The training one contained 60,000 status-rssi-distance tuples randomly chosen from the overall dataset, while the test one contained 20,000 tuples, also randomly selected among the overall 300,000 ones. These two datasets are disjoint (i.e. there is no observation repeated in both of them). After training the classifiers with the first dataset and testing them against the latter one, the predictive power metrics for each of them were obtained.

The True Positive Rate (TPR) and the True Negative Rate (TNR), also known, respectively, as sensitivity and specificity of the classifier, the F_1 Score and the Accuracy for the classification of Occupied parking spots (i.e. the actual positive condition is the presence of a vehicle in the spot) are presented in Table 3. As this is a binary classification problem (i.e. there can only be Occupied or Free status), False Positive Rate (FPR) can be extracted straightforward as $1 - TNR$. Moreover, Fig. 12 presents the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, which illustrates the diagnostic ability of the different classifiers (when predicting Occupied parking spots) as their discrimination threshold is varied. In particular, the highlighted point indicates the TPR and FPR for the maximum accuracy of the classification.

As it can be seen from the obtained results, the intuitively existing correlation that was observed between the parking spot status and the RSSI, has been actually demonstrated. In this respect, even though none of the classifiers are able to show a really high accuracy, the sensitivity for the case of occupied parking spots, is around 75% in all the cases. Respectively, F_1 Score and Accuracy figures for all the classifiers are also around 70%, which implies a reasonably high precision and accuracy on the predictions made. The key conclusion is that, specially for the case of a confirmation of the parking spot's *Occupied* status, the AI-based predictor can be used to solidly increase the level of confidence of such observation. Since the key idea to implement these predictors is to increase the confidence on the incoming observations, the performance shown by the classifiers, mainly the KNN and Decision Tree ones, should be enough to enrich the smart parking service by employing the available network-related information in order to attach to the sensor-based status data the predicted status.

Fig. 12. ROC curve for different classifiers on Occupied parking spots.

In conclusion, the analysis performed has demonstrated an interesting opportunity to optimize the behavior of IoT-based smart parking services through the cross-correlation of the actual sensor readings and, a priori unconnected information, such as the RSSI. Such a correlation can be modeled through properly trained AI-based classifiers, and attached (e.g. linking the resulting prediction as meta-data to the actual parking spot status reading) to the received sensor observation, so that the data consumer, and the service in general, is enriched. The evaluation that has been performed is specific for the analyzed parking service, but it could be explored for other services in which network-related information (e.g. packet losses, delay, etc.) may be correlated with the service-specific data.

7. Conclusions and future work

Within this paper we have presented the assessment of LoRaWAN technology behavior when employed for supporting the wireless communication of a Smart City service. In particular, a real-world deployment of a smart parking service has been used as the scenario for this thorough study.

Several conclusions can be derived from the results that have been presented in Section 4. Firstly, the performance of LoRaWAN networks, in terms of coverage and communication robustness, is far from the theoretical values when devices are deployed in dense urban areas, and

they can be even worse in presence of the special characteristics of Smart City services, where, for example in the smart parking case, cars parked over the sensors significantly degrade the signal strength.

However, it has been experimentally demonstrated that LoRaWAN can still be suitable for this type of services, as long as a careful deployment plan is carried out in advance. In this sense, for realizing robust and resilient large-scale LoRaWAN-based communications in urban scenarios, the results obtained during the evaluation described in the paper encourages the careful understanding of the radio propagation conditions (e.g. avoiding the use of simple propagation models but employing modeling tools that incorporates urban scenario features such as density and type of obstacles). In the case of the typical propagation environments that can be found in downtown urban areas the behavior observed in the analysis that has been performed recommends to deploy GWs in a picocell distribution, limiting the range covered per GW below 500 m.

The LoRa propagation model that has been derived in the paper should be considered as a useful tool for making the initial coarse planning of analogous deployments in urban scenarios. However, as it has been discussed in Section 5, after the analysis of the real-world data obtained during the experimental pilot, radio propagation in LoRa networks is heavily affected by the specific characteristics of urban scenarios. Thus, a thorough analysis of GW deployments, considering the orography of the area and the location of the GWs relative to the

area where the IoT devices will be deployed, has to be carried out. Whereas, in situations where LOS can be guaranteed (or, at least, GWs are deployed at high locations so immediate GW's surroundings can be considered free-space), LoRaWAN has demonstrated large coverage areas that could be analytically modeled, even considering the presence of large obstacles (i.e. cars) just over the IoT devices. However, GWs which are located too close to obstacles will suffer from further channel impairments, different from the bare propagation losses, which produce overall worse communication conditions and imply deficient coverage situation.

Thus, identifying key locations with good overview of the city (i.e. typically high points in the surroundings of the city) and placing there LoRa GWs, provides a good and efficient coverage to the underlying smart city services. While providing coverage to specific areas in the city would require a more detailed and ad-hoc understanding of the scenario to come up with an appropriate LoRa network infrastructure deployment plan.

Finally, the paper has practically demonstrated that understanding the insights that can be derived from the network-related information, is not only valuable at the service planning phase, but it can also optimize the actual service execution. As it has been presented in Section 6, applying data analytics to the available network-related information, specifically AI-based classifiers analyzing the RSSI data, could be a smart way to increase the confidence on the available service information. The solution that has been proposed and assessed in the paper should be taken as an example of the potential application of AI for cross-correlation of data for the sake of enriching smart services provision. While the case reported in the paper is exclusive for the smart parking service, other services, not only on the smart city domain, or for the LoRa technology, should explore the application of AI-based data analytics for the sake of service improvement.

As the future steps, we plan to evaluate in detail the coverage in the whole city, and compare our results with other datasets for LoRaWAN networks, such as the LoED dataset [29]. Besides, we also plan to gather more information within the different SFs with a longer dataset, forcing the use of higher SFs to compare the number of packets demodulated by the furthest GWs, exploring the limits of LoRaWAN in urban areas.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Juan Ramón Santana: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Software. **Pablo Sotres:** Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Formal analysis. **Jesús Pérez:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Data curation. **Luis Sánchez:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **Jorge Lanza:** Investigation, Software, Validation. **Luis Muñoz:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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